

A study about Genekampowermoleculer: an inexpensive highly potent antiviral molecule against pandemic coronaviruses (SARS CoV-2) for prevention and treatment options

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Summary: From Jan, 2020, there is a pandemic outbreak of coronaviruses (SARS CoV-2) going in the world. There is a need of an effective solution for prevention and treatment. In this work, a liquid solution from a plant called Genekampowermoleculer was developed, which is applied in oral cavity with a special procedure using buccal swabs during the course of infection in 9 cases and found to cure the corona virus infection fully. The persons taking this molecule as prophylaxis are showing that they donot get the infection, when they are visiting crowded areas like malls and parties in closed room without masks and social distancing now. Even in one case, one fully vaccinated person got full blown infection while she was working with non-vaccinated person, who was taking this molecule and has no infection before, during and after this incident. It was also found that this molecule may be used as preventive measurement also.

Conclusion: Genekampowermoleculer may be used for the treatment and prophylaxis of coronavirus infection. Bigger studies are needed to unfold its full potential.

Keywords: Coronavirus, Therapy, Medicinal plant, Prophylaxis, Antivirus, Virology

Background: Since January 2020, there is pandemic outbreak of coronaviruses (SARS CoV-2) from a Chinese city called Wuhan. (Zhang et al. 2019; Wu et al. 2020; Zhu et al. 2020). Real time PCR is one of the important detection methods to be used in pandemic outbreak as done in H1N1 outbreak in 2009. (Lee et al. 2009 and 2010). One of first commercial ready to use PCR kits was developed through Group of the author and it is found to have better than the assays recommended through World Health Organization (WHO). (Bhatia, 2023) A number of therapeutic molecules are developed and used. There was rush for making quick profits while offering solutions as WHO and many approvals agencies throughout the world go in action to do everything possible to stop this pandemic outbreak. Many therapies are approved. (Garcia-Vidal, 2022) The drugs like remdesivir, baricitinib, dexamethasone etc were used. Convalescent plasma therapy was suggested to be used as therapeutic option (Joyner et al. 2020, Cheragali et al. 2020). The success of this plasma therapy was shown and it is recommended to start it at the earlier stage. (Zheng et al. 2020)

The clinical use of antibodies like bamlanivimab and etesevimab (from Eli Lilly); cilgavimab and tixagevimab (from AstraZeneca); casirivimab and Imdevimab (from Regeneron); regdanvimab (from Celltrion); and sotrovimab (from GSK and Vir Biotechnology) were suggested. (Kumar et al. 2022, Niknam et al. 2022) Stem cell therapy to treat pneumonia was shown to be effective. (Meng et al. 2020). Low-dose radiation therapy for management of pneumonia was tried in clinical settings (Sanmamed et al. 2021) Different drug targeting pathways including important role of S-Protein as well as ACE2 for developing optimal therapeutic solution for coronaviruses were suggested and tried. (Zumla et al. 2016, Zhao et al. 2021)

Compounds from different plants are being used for treatment for many centuries in many countries around the world. These compounds are part and parcel of many developing countries. Many groups have done research to show that these plants may be used to treat the bacterial and viral infections

like influenza, corona, hepatitis, herpes viruses etc. (Sato et al. 1996, Cinati et al. 2003, Mirzaie et al 2020, Ali and Kunugi 2021, Ghoran et al. 2021, Khanna et al 2021, Lim et al. 2021, Oba et al. 2021, Sahel and Kanisah, 2021, Takayama et al. 2021, Park et al. 2022, Zrig, 2022)

There is detailed description of plants, which may be used for treatment of viral diseases. (Boukhatem and Setzer 2020) It is shown that there are plant-based molecules like 5-aminolevulinic acid, which can inhibit the coronaviruses effectively. (Tun el al. 2022) Advanced methods like molecular docking, molecular dynamic stimulations etc are used to show that these phytomolecules are in position to inhibit the specific parts of coronaviruses. (Zamzami 2023). In another research work, a natural compound called quercetin-3- β -galactoside was identified as an inhibitor of the protease by molecular docking, SPR/FRET-based bioassays, and mutagenesis studies. (Chen et al. 2006) A list of natural compounds effective against SARS CoV-2 like luteolin, sinigrin, tomentin, curcumin, lycorine, terpenes, lectins, licoleafol etc as well as an update of medicinal plants are discussed for clinical use. (Orhan et al. 2020, Jamal 2022)

There are reports of the use of multivitamins, which have been associated with clinical improvement in other infectious diseases, such as tuberculosis, dengue virus and HIV. (Yam et al 2020)

ACE2 is well known receptor for SARS CoV-2 virus as this is entry port to different kinds of tissues. This is available in abundant in oral cavity particularly in cells of the tongue. It is also available on upper respiratory tract, hence the people suffering from the coronaviral infection has symptoms to related to upper respiratory tract like pain, needle pricking like effect. Loss of the smell anosmia and loss of taste ageusia are two signs in many patients because the virus effects ACE2, which is present in the sensory tissues of oral cavity and nose. (Salamana et al. 2020, Sayan et al. 2020, Xu et al. 2020, Ashraf et al. 2021)

Our laboratory is working for last 10 years for searching molecule as antiviral options. During the literature search many years ago, some of plants were identified as interesting targets for viral therapy. We decided to develop an oral plant-based solution to prevent and treat the coronavirus infection as it is simple to use.

Methods: An extract was created through adding powder from a plant in a liquid. The quality control was conducted that this extract does not have any bacterial contamination. This extract was pipetted in 1 ml tubes and labelled as Genekampowermolecule. It was stored at 4 °C as well as room temperature. It was found that this is stable for many months without the loss of quality. (The data about the development molecule cannot be shown because of possibility of patents, if any)

There were 12 persons, which have decided to take this molecule in three different stages of coronavirus infection: before the infection as a preventive option, right from the beginning of the infection as well as during the infection. The consents of these persons are taken in order to participate in this study.

Each person was asked daily to communicate with us about the effects after the taking the molecule orally as well as testing for presence of SARS CoV-2 with rapid test as well as PCR test to document the developments as well as effects of molecule.

Oral procedure for application of the molecule: As it is known that ACE2 receptors are present abundantly on tongues and oral cavity, hence the persons was asked to use buccal swab, which was rinsed in the 1 ml tube containing Genekampowermolecule. This molecule rinsed swab was applied on inner as well as outer gingiva (free and attached) of all teeth in maxilla and mandible regions. After this, the rinsed buccal swab was rubbed on the dorsum of the tongue covering apex, body as well as upper part of oral cavity (anterior hard palate and posterior soft palate). The rest fluid was

put on the dorsum of the tongue. The volume used per application was between 500 to 700 µl. The teeth were cleared before the use as this is an important requirement. The user was not allowed to take anything within 45 minutes after the molecule application. As a preventive tool, it was taken 2 or 3 times a week or before visiting a crowded area e.g., a larger social gathering in a closed room.

In case of therapeutic option: It was taken immediately after the onset of symptoms or during the advanced symptoms e.g., severe coughing or with fever with joint pain as well as headache. In the case of symptoms, users took also antipyretic drugs like paracetamol.

Each person took multivitamin tablets from drug stores. In case of preventive measurement, multivitamin was taken once a week. In case of onset of symptoms, multivitamin tablets were taken once a day daily for 4-6 days depending on the illness course.

During the illness, each person was recommended to do 3- or 4-times daily mouth wash with luke warm water containing cooking salt. It was recommended to clear the teeth before applying the Genekampowermolecule. After that one should not eat for 45 minutes or go sleep at night.

Results: The results of 9 persons are presented here. They were from different countries like Germany, India and USA during the different waves of pandemic outbreak.

All infected persons have coughing, headache, fever, pressure on ears as well as needle pricking like effect (pain) in throat. One of first effect from the molecule was reduction in headache, pain in the throat e.g., needle pricking like effect. All told that pain in the throat was reduced within 2-3 hours after oral administration. The summary of detailed data is shown in Table 1.

Person 1 is taking this molecule for last 3 years on regular basis with multivitamin once a week. He suffered corona infection last June, 2022 as he stopped taking this molecule and went to attend an open-air party, where he got infected with coronavirus. He got the throat pain and fever as well as headache and took 3 times daily this molecule for 5 days with paracetamol as well as multivitamin tablets daily. The symptoms went away, but dry coughing took 2 weeks to go away. He is not vaccinated.

He was taking this molecule after November 2022, when he was going to crowded mall during X-mas or party without taking any mask. Till today he never got any kind of coronavirus infection.

He was with person 2 during 15th February, 2023 as he was taking regularly this molecule. Person 2 got coronavirus infection in spite of 3 times vaccination with mRNA vaccines. He did not get any infection in spite he is not vaccinated.

Person 2: she is vaccinated 3 times with mRNA vaccine (Pfizer). She has never experienced any previous infection because she always wore the mask and took precautions. She stopped taking these precautions during January and February 2023. On 16.2.23 she got his first full blown infection with symptoms like headache, running nose, fever, pain in the joints etc. She took the molecule once a day with multivitamin, her symptoms started reducing immediately, she recovered within 6 days. The running nose symptom was away within 4 days after taking molecule.

Person 3 (vaccinated) had a very severe coughing as well as running nose along with pricking needle like effect in throat with pain. He might have this infection as he was visiting a pub after getting his first vaccine. There was reduction in the frequency as well as intensity of coughing within 2 days after taking the molecule, but in this case, the pain and pricking needle effect were reduced within 2-3 hours after taking the molecule. Running nose was reduced strongly within 3-4 days. He was positive for coronavirus PCR test, but negative for rapid test in September, 2021.

Person 4 (not vaccinated) was residing in a house, where many residents were suffering from coronaviral infection in March 2022 and they were tested positive with PCR as well as rapid tests. This person was taking daily Genekampowermolecule before going to sleep and after cleaning the teeth. He was going for rapid testing because of visiting his old parent. He was found positive in the rapid test. He was confirmed with real time PCR positive indicating very high viral load as well as coronavirus specific PCR test from Genekam. But he was showing hardly any symptoms that his attending physician was very surprised. Only symptoms were light pain in throat and fever for one night at the onset of infection. He took the molecule and he was negative within 4 days.

This person visited an exhibition in September 2022 in German city called Essen with FFP mark without taking molecule. He got mild symptoms like slight fever, pain in throat etc on the following day, but he took molecule and multivitamins, the symptoms were away within the following 2 days.

Person 5: she has suffered delta virus infection wave in India and coronavirus infection was confirmed with rapid test and PCR test positive, but she took this molecule with paracetamol and recovered within 7 days. After that she was twice vaccinated and suffered severe coronavirus infection in September, 2022. She recovered as she took Genekampowermolecule also. She suffered also loss of taste and loss of smell.

Person 6: she is a German nurse and 3 times vaccinated. She got severe infection with symptoms like severe head ache, fever, coughing, pressure on the ears and weakness. She was rapid test and real time PCR test positive. Her symptoms were getting severe. She took the molecule for 7 days. Her intensity of coughing reduced as well as head ache went away. She recovered within 7 days.

Person 7: she is 82 years old and suffering from diabetes. She is three times vaccinated. She got the infection and she took the molecule and recovered.

Person 8: he is also 83 years old and suffering from heart disease. He is also three times vaccinated. He got the coronavirus infection and took the molecule and recovered.

Person 9: he was suffering from throat pain for 3 days, he decided to take this molecule. The throat pain and itching inside the upper respiratory tract remains there, but this sputum turns yellow, therefore he was prescribed antibiotics for full recovery. He was not tested for coronavirus; it seems that he was suffering from bacterial infection as he responded to antibiotics prescribed through his physician.

None of the persons taken this molecule has complained any side effects during administration period or after that. This is very positive sign about the safety of this molecule, which is developed from natural source. All persons infected coronavirus as shown in table 1 got recovered.

Table 1 showing the details of participants and effect of Genekampowermolecule.

Participant	Gender	Vaccination status	Oral administration of molecule	SARS CoV-2 infection	Full recovery
1	Male	Not vaccinated	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Female	Vaccinated	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	Male	Vaccinated	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	Male	Not vaccinated	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Female	Vaccinated	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Female	Vaccinated	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Female	Vaccinated	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	Male	Vaccinated	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	Male	Vaccinated	Yes	Not tested	Not applicable

Discussion: In this research work, we have provided enough evidences that Genekampowermolecule is in position to be used for therapeutic and preventive option with safety. The results are encouraging us to think how to use molecule at wide scale and how this molecule should be approved for therapeutic as well as preventive use. There are many groups of persons, which are at risk for getting coronavirus infection e.g., dental surgeons, hospital workers, clinic staff, train staff, teachers, students, supermarket staff, police, army, journalists etc. This research is building basis for an inexpensive product against the costs of recombinant antibodies or protease inhibitors, which are complex in development and production, hence available only to a small population in the world. Genekampowermolecule can be produced at larger scale and it can serve as the first line of defense in the battle against pandemic coronaviruses. To our knowledge, there is hardly any molecule or product, which can be used for prevention of coronavirus infection except masks along with preventive measurements like social distancing. This molecule may help people to feel comfort and secure while working together with other persons in the office. The cost for production of 10 ml is around 3-5 Euro as this is sufficient for one treatment or multiple prevention doses for 1- 2 months. It can be reduced for developing countries, if raw material is sourced in bulk.

In our studies, combination of multivitamins and Genekampowermolecule have shown its effectiveness in the prophylaxis as well as treatment of the coronavirus infection against the studies conducted about the effectiveness of micronutrients only, where only moderate effect is seen in women. (Louca et al. 2021) This work also tries to use that vitamin B complex, Vitamin D and its combination with Zinc, which have no effect (data not shown), therefore all person took only multivitamins. The intake of vitamin supplements has shown to be effectiveness in reduction in Ebola patients. (Yam et al. 2020) Our studies also support the effectiveness of multivitamins.

Further work for us is to determine how long one can use this molecule without any side effects and to know whether this molecule can be effective against other respiratory viral infections e.g., influenza, respiratory syncytial virus and other corona viruses.

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